

Deliverable D7.3

**PEDR including communication activities,
reviewed version**

Deliverable information

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Executive Summary

This is the first publicly available Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of project Results including Communication activities (PEDRC). The deliverable presents non-confidential information, results and designs that have been undertaken the first 6-month period of BIOSYSMO in context of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. EXE is the leader of Tasks 7.1 and 7.2 undertaking the analyses and activities for project communication-dissemination and clustering; AXIA is leading WP7 and Tasks 7.3 and 7.4 following the analyses and planning of the project results exploitation and IPR management.

Regarding dissemination & communication activities (T7.1 and T7.2) within this deliverable the relevant audiences that are being targeted are going to be presented, as well as all communication and dissemination materials and tools developed, including the project website and social media platforms. Moreover, attendance and organisation of events, conferences, workshops, training and teaching activities are also going to be summarised. Publications in high impact journals aiming to the dissemination of the BIOSYSMO results will be summarised, along with all repositories that will be employed serving for storage of open access information.

Furthermore, with respect to exploitation and management of IPRs (T7.3 and T7.4), this deliverable focusses on the analysis of BIOSYSMO applications, for which there is direct exploitation and commercial interest. Additionally, the product presents the external environments (SWOT and market landscape) and provides a detailed discussion of the exploitation routes and IPR means considered to protect and effectively exploit the key exploitable results of the project. The potential impacts at environmental, policymakers and partners levels are also identified and discussed.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
KoM	Kick of meeting
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
KERs	Key Exploitable results
D&C	Dissemination and exploitation
PEDRC	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results including Communication activities

1 Introduction

Deliverable D7.3 was compiled in the framework of WP7: Communication, dissemination and exploitation, which aims to: (i) promote the project among the general community to increase awareness and visibility, (ii) ensure that the results will reach relevant stakeholders, with emphasis on key exploitable results, (iii) identify the most appropriate target groups with high interest in BIOSYSMO's results, (iv) develop business models and define appropriate exploitation routes, and (v) establish synergies and clustering activities with relevant ongoing research projects.

The aim of this plan is to set the ground for communication and dissemination activities of the project, raising the importance of pollutants degradation with microorganisms, with the aid of a computationally assisted framework for designing and optimising synergistic biosystems. The overall goal of this plan is to increase the visibility of the project and promote the exchange of knowledge regarding bioremediation technologies while attracting potential end users. The project's objectives and outcomes are being communicated via printed material, biannual newsletters, press releases, participation to events, and training activities. Furthermore, dissemination is being carried out through the organisation and attendance of major events in the field of bioremediation, as well as through publications in peer-reviewed journals. Specific tools reach different audiences to maximise their engagement.

Moreover, the exploitation plan aims to investigate, analyse, and highlight all aspects that can affect the exploitation potential of BIOSYSMO results. A presentation of all these aspects unfolds in this deliverable in the scope of an application-based approach, where individual results apparently formulate the conceptual and tangible nature of end-user project applications. Overall, (i) the five BIOSYSMO applications are described in terms of provided products & services; (ii) the associated key markets (size, growth, trends, and segments) and the key strengths and weaknesses are identified and discussed; (iii) the positive impacts to the environment and policymaking are spotted; (iv) the commercial and noncommercial partner profiles are presented, (v) the potential exploitation routes followed by the different types of partners are identified and described, and (vi) the IPR management plan and available means for protection of the different BIOSYSMO results are identified and analysed.

This deliverable is the first version of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan and will be continuously updated and improved during the project implementation. Two follow-up deliverables will be submitted depicting the progress made, as well as updating on any adjustments made to the plan aiming to improve the strategy followed, based on the knowledge gained throughout the project.

2 Dissemination and communication plan

2.1 General strategy and objectives

Dissemination activities aim to maximise the impact of research results by sharing them to a target audience that includes academia, stakeholders, industry, policy makers, civil society, etc. Dissemination aims at: i. Awareness raising and sharing the concept of the project with its audience, ii. Information and education of the community; iii. Engaging the community and iv. Promoting the project results¹.

Communication activities go beyond dissemination, aim at raising awareness, and target the wider public, including the media. It is important to highlight in a non- technical language the objectives and expected outcomes of the project to be easily understood by the audience. Messages should be clear and easy to understand and should be tailored to the receiver(s).

Under BIOSYSMO specific tools will be implemented in order to broaden the target audience and increase the engagement in the progress and advancements². These tools and channels are summarised in Figure 1. In particular, communication tools, already designed, include the visual identity (logo, colours identity, fonds, templates), project website, leaflets and flyers, social media, videos, press releases, newsletters, etc. Dissemination actions, on the other hand, include participation or organisation of workshops, conferences, training sessions, clustering interviews/meetings, etc.

Then the target audiences and stakeholders will be reached as summarised in the next section of the deliverable. Moreover, researchers from similar projects working in the field of bioremediation and computational modelling will be contacted with the aim of forming a cluster of projects and broadening the scientific network. Knowledge transfer and open discussions within the cluster will take place drafting a roadmap for participation in common activities and research initiatives among others.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/health/beneficiaries-corner/documents/factsheet-06.pdf>

² https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/health/beneficiaries-corner/documents/overview-dissemination-methods_en.pdf

Figure 1. BIOSYSMO strategic tools and audiences.

2.2 Types of audiences

Dissemination and Communication activities in order to be effective should focus to different audiences and convey audience-specific messages.

The general public (Citizens) will always be the main target audience for communication activities. Messages to the general public will be shared in a comprehensive language focussing on the actual impact research can have on daily life, providing evidence on how the general public can benefit from research activities. Other target groups to be reached include the civil society, institutions and the research community, industry and investors as well as relevant authorities, etc. Figure 2 summarised the communication audiences according to the EU Commission guidelines.

Figure 2. Targeted EU communication audiences.

On the other hand, dissemination activities will target the end-users community, scientific community, policy makers, environmental NGOs, students and the wider public and the society.

The related key messages to be communicated to these target groups can be found in Deliverable 7.2 of this project, titled: Communication tools. In particular, for BIOSYSMO the research focus areas would be bioremediation, microbiology, synthetic biology, bioinformatics, and environmental science, while end users interested in the BIOSYSMO technologies are environmental consulting companies; industries responsible for water and soil pollution, plant breeders, and microbial inoculant producers. Moreover, dissemination of research is also important in reaching the broader public, sharing news beyond publications and research achievements that are described in an easy-to-understand manner. Figure 3 summarised the dissemination audiences.

Figure 3. Targeted dissemination audiences.

2.3 Dissemination & Communication

As summarised previously, the main objective of the dissemination and communication strategy is the participation of stakeholders to maximise the impact of the project results, while in the initial phase of the project, communication activities will focus on the creation of awareness of the project. In the following phases, highlighting the results and improving the participation in project actions will be in the BIOSYSMO's team focus.

Various dissemination actions are envisaged during the project to increase the impact of the project results. The following graph presents in a schematic manner the main dissemination and communication activities.

Figure 4. Dissemination and Communication activities.

Table 1 presents in detail all the communication and dissemination activities along with the target KPIs and the actions already implemented. This table will be continuously updated throughout the project and serves as a monitoring tool for progress made. So far, the reached KPIs are summarised in the following table.

Table 1. Dissemination and Communication KPIs.

Actions	Description	Target KPI	KPIs reached
Communication activities			
Visual identity	Logo, design chart, templates for presentations, deliverables, etc.	Designed and used in all materials	Done
Project website	containing information on the project partners, research activities, main achievements, etc.	Updated monthly, 600 visits/yr	Done, Designed and announced
Social media	Presence in LinkedIn and Twitter	At least 40 posts/yr	Done 22 posts in each platform the first 6M

Online articles by partners	Publication of news items from the project in partner's website and social media accounts	A least 2 items/yr per partner	21 actions in first 6M
Leaflet, brochure	Designed for distribution in fairs, conferences etc.	10 distributed	Done, Designed and shared
Poster, roll-up	M6, aiming at project's awareness; M24 and M44, for transferability and exploitation of results	M6, M24, M44 Displayed in 5 events	Done, First roll and poster designed and printed
Digital newsletter	Distributed through e-mail and relevant online platforms	2 releases/ 250 subscribers	First Newsletter in progress
Press releases	Describing the main project objectives and outcomes and communicated to key media actors	First by M6, least 3 by M46	Done by UBU in national press and more
Project videos	One during year 1 to promote the project and another during year 4 focused on results	2 videos	-
Dissemination activities			
Events	- Participation in conferences and industrial fairs	>15 conferences	-
Workshops and webinars	- Participation - 1 internal session for sharing knowledge - 1 event to develop synergies with other projects in the same topic - 1 technical conference to attract industries and customers	3 organised, 15-20 attendees each	Participated in 2
Publications	peer-reviewed, open access publications	>25 articles submitted	2 already published
Research training	MSc/PhD theses related to the project research; university course materials; summer school seminars	>10 MSc, >5 PhD theses; >400 students reached	-
Networking activities	Through memberships, associations and relevant EC events	10 actions	

Clustering activities	Co-organized workshops or webinars; attendance to events of similar EU actions, Horizon Europe brokerage events, etc.	3 joint actions	1 finalised, 1 expected
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2.3.1 Dissemination and Communication Questionnaire

In order to collect information from partners, different types of questionnaires are going to be shared with the consortium engaging everyone in dissemination and communication activities.

The first questionnaire was already shared with the consortium to map the partners' intentions in future dissemination actions (events, publications, training activities), inform the consortium of any already finalised actions (online announcements, events participation), as well as updating the list of networks and similar initiatives with which the BIOSYSMO project has interactions.

The questionnaire can be found [here](#).

Regular questionnaires will be shared with the consortium every two months, mapping the dissemination and communication activities performed. In all dissemination activities the audience size and type (e.g. Research communities, Industry, business partners, innovators, EU Institutions, Citizens, etc.) are monitored. In communication activities, the target audience, the communication channel (e.g. Event, Exhibition, Interview, Media Article, website etc.) and some important KPIs (e.g. audience size, no of flyers distributed, etc.) are reported.

In addition, another type of questionnaire will be shared to collect the progress of consortiums in project activities in a simple and elaborative way to be included in the Newsletter issues.

Figure 5. Dissemination and Communication questionnaire.

All information is kept in an internal consortium repository where the following information is stored:

- BIOSYSMO Publications
- BIOSYSMO Dissemination activities
- BIOSYSMO Communication activities
- BIOSYSMO Upcoming Events
- BIOSYSMO Relevant Projects, Clusters, and Associations

2.3.2 Dissemination and communication collaboration

The BIOSYSMO's Dissemination Plan, already agreed upon by the partners, includes the identification of the communication means and dissemination objectives as well as the intended level of engagement: information, consultation, interaction and collaboration. Figure 6 summarises the pathways for sharing information collaboratively and individually among the consortium and with the targeted audiences.

Figure 6. Collaboration among the consortium.

2.3.3 Visual identity

The project logo and identity are finalised and included in Deliverable 7.1: Visual identity, website, and social media accounts. Therefore, a visual brand and a package of templates are delivered and will facilitate the promotion and dissemination of the project. The project logo is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Logo of the BIOSYSMO project.

Followingly, a ppt presentation template will help the consortium present its results in meetings and beyond. Social media templates have been designed to support dedicated posts, either presenting the project concept, the consortium, project materials, or announcing an activity.

Furthermore, a Deliverable template, an Agenda template, the List of Participants, the Meeting Minutes, the consent photography form and the Meeting Badges have been designed as seen in Figure 8.

All templates can be found in the dedicated section of the [project website](#).

Project templates

PPT presentation

Social media template

Deliverable template

Agenda template

List of Participants

Meeting Minutes

Figure 8. BIOSYSMO project templates.

2.3.4 Project website

The website acts as the primary interface for the public to inform them about the concept, progress, actions and results of the project. The website link is: www.biosysmo.eu

The website information will be updated periodically. In particular, news and events, dissemination materials (available for download), newsletters, public deliverables, and open-access publications will be kept within the website as a repository. Website statistics are going to be monitored over the project course.

Figure 9. BIOSYSMO website.

2.3.5 Social media

The social media accounts on LinkedIn and Twitter are already launched and updated weekly. More than 20 posts have already been posted on both social networks during the first 6 months. The posts include the announcement of the project, important meetings, including the KoM, the project impacts, press releases from the partners, while the introduction of the consortium has started and will continue on a weekly basis. Statistics for the audiences reached, the views, the engagement, etc. are going to be monitored for both social media platforms. The accounts links can be found below:

2.3.6 Online articles and other communication activities

The consortium communicates to the dissemination manager all communication activities performed on on on on the consortium's social media, website, or other media such as the press or networking events. Table 2 summarises those activities.

Table 2. Overall communication activities carried out by the consortium.

Partner	Date: DD/MM/YY	Description	Target audience	Communication channel
BSY	17-Jun-22	BIOSYSMO grant announcement on twitter	Citizens	Social Media
BSY	03-Oct-22	BIOSYSMO KOM announcement on twitter	Citizens	Social Media
EXE	03-Oct-22	BIOSYSMO project announcement on the company website	Citizens	Website
EXE	03-Oct-22	BIOSYSMO KOM announcement on LinkedIn	Citizens	Social Media
EXE	03-Oct-22	BIOSYSMO KOM announcement on twitter	Citizens	Social Media
EXE	03-Oct-22	BIOSYSMO KOM announcement on twitter	Citizens	Social Media
BSY	03-Oct-22	Website post	Industry	Website
BSY	03-Oct-22	Social media post	Citizens	Social Media
IDE	08-Nov-22	MicroTechWeek 2022	Industry	Event
UBU	23-Sep-22	Press release on the University of Burgos website and sent to the Media - BIOSYSMO presentation.	Civil society	Press release
UBU	23-Sep-22	Media impact example in press release	Civil society	Media Article
UBU	23-Sep-22	Publication of social media on press release (LI, TW, FB)	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	23-Sep-22	Social media publication on press release (LI, TW, FB)	Civil society	Social Media

UBU	29-Sep-22	Social media publications on seminar (communication)	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	29-Sep-22	Social media publications on seminar (communication)	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	7-11 Nov 2022	BIOSYSMO as co-organiser of the MicroTechWeek. Event- dissemination. Promotion-communication.	Research communities	Event
UBU	07-Nov-22	Press realease on MicroTechWeek (BIOSYSMO logo)	Civil society	Press release
UBU	11/18/2022	Press release on MicroTechWeek (afterwards)	Civil society	Press release
UBU	08-Nov-22	Social media publications on MicroTechWeek (afterwards)	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	05-Dec-22	Newspaper article - print media El Correo de Burgos (online not yet)	Civil society	Media Article
UBU	12-Dec-22	Social media publications on El Correo de Burgos	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	12-Dec-22	Social media rehare on El Correo de Burgos	Civil society	Social Media
UBU	17-Nov-22	Video summary on MicroTechWeek (BIOSYSMO logo)	Civil society	Video

2.3.7 Printed material: leaflet, brochure, roll-up, poster

Printed material is already developed and presented in Deliverable 7.2: Communication tools. This material includes an A5 leaflet, the official brochure, the roll up and the poster, as summarised in Figure 10. The printed material is distributed at various conferences, exhibitions, and networking events to promote the project.

Printed material	
BIOSYSMO Leaflet	BIOSYSMO Brochure
BIOSYSMO poster	BIOSYSMO roll-up

2.3.8 Figure 10. BIOSYSMO printed material. Digital newsletter

The BIOSYSMO newsletter is to be published every six months. Overall, 8 issues are announced. The objective is to inform stakeholders of the latest project news. The target audience will be mainly Industry, environmental organisations, academia, policy makers, investors, and the public. A website subscription to the newsletter is already available. In order to increase the engagement LinkedIn newsletters are going to be shared while subscriptions are going to be collected on the LinkedIn platform as well. Newsletters will be distributed by email to all subscribers via the website, as well as to other target groups that have been identified, and will also be shared as notifications to emails and LinkedIn accounts to all LinkedIn registrants.

Table 3. Newsletter release planning.

Newsletter Issue	Delivery date
Issue 1	March 2023
Issue 2	August 2023
Issue 3	February 2024
Issue 4	August 2024
Issue 5	February 2025
Issue 6	August 2025
Issue 7	February 2026
Issue 8	August 2026

2.3.9 Press releases

According to our plan at least 4 press releases are expected. The first one has already been released until M6 by our partner University of Burgos. At least three more are expected to arrive at the end of the project.

The first press release was announced in the Burgos regional newspaper (El Correo de Burgos). In this announcement in Spanish, members of the team from ICCRAM center from University of Burgos, presented the kick start of the BIOSYSMO project providing more details on their work toward soil and

water decontamination through the development of innovative and sustainable technologies. The article will soon be available online.

Figure 11. BIOSYSMO project in press announced by University of Burgos.

2.3.10 Project videos

During the project, two (2) videos are expected to be developed. The first video is going to be released towards the end of the first year. The first video will include the main project information and will elaborate the project concept and objectives, highlighting the impacts to society and beyond. The last video will aim to showcase the project results in close collaboration with the consortium, providing direct input and footage from their premises and their advancements of work. The target groups for the videos will be the General Public, Citizens & End User Communities, Public Authorities, Associations and especially for the final video the scientific community as well.

The videos will be uploaded to YouTube and the project website, while they will also be announced on social networks. The video views will be monitored and reported in this section.

Figure 12. Expected BIOSYSMO videos.

2.3.11 Conferences, Workshops and Events

The BIOSYSMO consortium will attend several conferences, exhibitions, fairs, and networking events in order to disseminate the project results, using scientific presentations and posters. The project's material (flyer, brochures, poster) can be presented at these targeted events. During the course of the project, participation in at least 15 conferences and industrial fairs is expected.

Conferences and trade fairs of interest identified by BIOSYSMO consortium are the following:

International Conference on Bioremediation of Contaminated Soils, European Bioremediation Conference; World Congress of Soil Science; AquaconSoil; CONDEGRES; EUROSIL; ENSOR; International Congress on Plant Molecular Biology; ISMET Conferences; IWA Leading Edge Conference on Water and Wastewater Technologies; Synthetic Biology UK; Gordon Conference in Synthetic Biology; SEED conferences; Microbiology Society; Society for Applied Microbiology; International Conference on Bioremediation Engineering and Research; World Congress of Soil Science; IUFRO Tree Biotechnology Conference; Joint Meeting of the Spanish Society of Plant Biology and the Spanish Portuguese Congress on Plant Biology; Spanish Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology; Meeting of Spanish Plant Molecular Biology; International Society for Microbial Ecology Symposium; International Conference on Microbial Fuel Cells and Reactor Design; International Conference on Environmental Pollution and Remediation; SETAC meetings; EFB events.

Regarding organisation of workshops, the consortium was asked through the first dissemination questionnaire for their intentions and the following partners already agreed on workshops: Blue Synergy, CIIMAR, University of Burgos (ICCRAM), and Jozef Stefan Institute. The list will be updated with more partners willing to share their results with the scientific community, industry, local and national authorities, end users, and other relevant stakeholders. Over the project duration participation in several Workshops and webinars is expected while the organisation of the following events is also planned:

- 1 internal session for sharing knowledge

- 1 event to develop synergies with other projects in the same topic
- 1 technical conference to attract industries and customers

Each workshop should be organised by the consortium with the participation and presentation of the project technical partners, with a participation of at least 15-20 attendees.

The overall list of events will be continuously updated, ensuring that the set KPIs will be met.

2.3.11.1 Past activities

Table 4. Finalised dissemination activities.

No	Partner	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of dissemination activity	Further Specification	Partner's Role	Date/Period	Place
1	IDE	MicroTechWeek 2022 training	Education and training events	Presentation	Participation	09-Nov-22	Ljubljana (online)
2	UBU	UBU organises a seminar given by JSI partners.	Other	Presentation	Organization	29-Sep-22	Burgos (Spain)
3	UBU	MicroTechWeek 2022	Education and training events	Presentation	Organization	7-11 Nov 2022	Ljubljana (Slovenia)

2.3.11.2 Planned activities

Table 5. Planned dissemination activities of the consortium.

No	Partner	Event	Year	Date: DD/MM	Location	Website
1	UBFC	<u>SETAC conference</u>	2023	30 Apr - 3 May	Dublin	https://europe2023.setac.org/
2	CIIMAR	IMAB23 (International Congress on Metal-microbe applications for circular economy),	2023	19-21 Apr	Porto	https://imab23.ciimar.up.pt/
3	JSI	IMAB23 (International Congress on Metal-microbe applications for circular economy),	2023	19-21 Apr	Porto	https://imab23.ciimar.up.pt/
4	IDE, AXIA, EXE	BioRemid 2023	2023	29-30 Jun	Muttenz, Switzerland	https://biotechnet.ch/network/event/bioremid2023/

5	UBU	AquaConSoil Conference 2023	2023	11-15 Septemb er	Prague (Czech Republic)	https://www.aquaconsoil.com/aquaconsoil-2023/
6	JSI	Trends in Microbial Solutions for Sustainable Agriculture	2023	13 – 15 Sept	Serbia	https://www.icgeb.org/trends-in-microbial-solutions-workshop-serbia-2023/
7	JSI	FEMS Hamburg	2023	9 - 13 July	Hamburg	https://www.fems2023.org/

2.3.12 Publications

The results and findings of the implementation of the project will be published in peer-reviewed publications by the consortium. The publication in full open-access journals will be favoured, although specific hybrid journals with a high impact in their field will also be considered as a quest for the highest impact of the project results. 25 articles are expected and so far the following journals have been identified as potential media for publications:

Open Access: Open research Europe, Frontiers journals, PLOS journals, MDPI journals, Nature Communications, Microbial Biotechnology, eLife, Scientific Reports, Plant Biotechnology, Journal, Advanced Science, Water Research X, Energies, Environment International;

Renowned hybrid journals: Environmental Science & Technology, Nature Microbiology, ACS Synthetic, Biology, Environmental Microbiology, J. of Cleaner Production, Chemosphere, J. of Hazardous Materials, Environmental Research, Science of the Total Environment, PNAS, Plant Journal, Plant Physiology, Nature, ISME Journal, Small, ACS Nano, Water Research, J. of Power Sources, J. of Environmental & Chemical Engineering, J. of Soils and Sediments, Soil Biology and Biochemistry, International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment.

Figure 13. EU flag.

Regarding the publication procedure, the guidelines described in the Consortium Agreement will be followed, where it is clearly stated that a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 45 days advance notice to other beneficiaries. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing

the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt
 the support of the EU and the

of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted. The project should also acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement. The consortium will ensure immediate open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications generated in the project via the project website dedicated area, onto the following links.

Figure 14. BIOSYSMO repositories.

Zenodo³, an OpenAIRE⁴ compliant repository, and when appropriate in partner's institutional repositories (e.g., HAL⁵, RiUBU⁶, dat@UBFC⁷, e-cienciaDatos⁸). Each partner will provide information about any research output, tool or instrument needed to validate the conclusions of the publication via the repositories. More, repositories to be used related to data storage (eg. nucleotide sequences, DNA based fungal species etc.) can be found in the dedicated Data Management Plan Deliverable 8.2.

Currently already 2 publications acknowledging the BIOSYSMO project have been published in peer reviewed open access journals, as summarised in the following.

Table 6. BIOSYSMO Publications.

No	Partner	Title	Journal	DOI	Open Access (Y/N)
1	ICL	The production of selenium nanoparticles occurs through an interconnected pathway of sulphur metabolism and the response to	Microbial Biotechnology	10.1111/1751-7915.14215	Y

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁵ <https://hal.science/>

⁶ <https://riubu.ubu.es/>

⁷ <https://search-data.ubfc.fr/>

⁸ <https://edatos.consociomadrono.es/>

		oxidative stress in Pseudomonas putida KT2440			
2	ICL	The water potential governs the effector specificity of the transcriptional regulator XylR of Pseudomonas putida	Environmental Microbiology	10.1111/1462-2920.16342	Y

2.3.13 Training

The consortium will organise dedicated research trainings and educational activities aiming at the participation of students and young researchers, and aims to educate >10 MSc, >5 PhD theses and in general reach more than 400 students. A list of such activities will be kept in this section. Research fields that could be covered include:

- Surface and Colloid biotechnology
- Bioremediation technologies
- Microbiology
- Synthetic biology
- Bioinformatics
- Environmental science

2.3.14 Networking and outreach activities

Networking activities with other European projects are crucial for the successful dissemination and communication of the project⁹. Already a list of relevant projects has been identified (see section below) targeting to organising and participating in clustering events. Throughout the project 10 relevant actions are expected to be finalised, engaging the consortium's network with associations, memberships and relevant initiatives. Partners have already drafted a list of potential outreach actions, including:

- UBFC's living lab¹⁰
- CIIMAR's annual Open Day¹¹
- UBUMaker activities¹²
- CBGP's Plant Day activities¹³
- JSI Open Day

⁹ <https://eucalls.net/blog/how-to-network-for-eu-projects>

¹⁰ <https://chrono-environnement.univ-fcomte.fr/spip.php?page=projet&projet=60&lang=en>

¹¹ <https://www2.ciimar.up.pt/events.php?id=131>

¹² <https://laestacioncyt.es/>

¹³ <https://plantday18may.org/>

- TAUW Soil Seminar
- European Researcher's Night
- Pint of Science
- LEITAT's BES workshops

2.3.15 Clustering activities

Clustering activities aim at bringing together EU initiatives sharing same concepts, ideas and challenges, in specific co-organised meetings and events, enhancing their collaboration in research activities and dissemination actions. Clusters can benefit from such synergies by achieving the exchange of technical information and results in a confidentiality framework; broaden their network of collaboration in the European but also national and regional level; maximising the dissemination and communication of each project to the other projects and initiatives of the cluster and setting the ground for successful exploitation activities.

Within BIOSYSMO, a dedicated [website section](#) is developed that highlights the relevant projects. The table below summarises these initiatives including our sister projects and previous granted projects in the field of bioremediation. Already, the consortium has established communication with the relevant projects and is planning to participate in a common event within 2023. During the first 6 months of the project, BIOSYSMO was also presented in the [MicroTechWeek](#) organised by the GREENER and SURFBIO H2020 projects.

Over the course of the project, 3 joint actions are overall planned.

Table 7. Cluster projects and initiatives.

No	Topic	Title	Project	Cordis
1	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-10	Symbiotic, circular bioremediation systems and biotechnology solutions for improved environmental, economic, and social sustainability in pollution control	SYMBIOREM	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060361
2	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-10	New system-driven bioremediation of polluted habitats and the environment	NYMPHE	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060625
3	CE-BIOTECH-08-2020	Enhanced in situ bioremediation for contaminated land remediation	EiCLaR	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/965945

4	CE-BIOTEC-04-2018	InteGRated systems for Effective ENviroNmentAl Remediation	GREENER	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/826312
5	CE-BIOTEC-04-2018	Electricity-Driven Low Energy and Chemical Input Technology for Accelerated Bioremediation	ELECTRA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/826244
6	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-07	Toolbox for Microbiome based Remediation	MIBIREM	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059260

Other clustering activities may include liaisons with the following: Bio-based Industries Consortium, Society for Applied Microbiology, World Resources Forum, European Federation of Biotechnology, International Society for Microbial Electrochemistry and Technology, Spanish Society of Plant Biology, Spanish Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, IUFRO Tree Biotechnology Community, American Society for Microbiology, European Colloid & Interface Society, Federation of European, Microbiological Societies, Microbiology Society UK, Slovenian Microbiology Society, NICOLE Network, Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry, European Federation of Biotechnology, Enterprise Europe Network.

3 Exploitation plan

The BIOSYSMO exploitation plan aims to effectively transfer the key project results to the market in accordance with the individual exploitation routes and IPRs identified for each Key Exploitable Results (KER). This initial plan focusses specifically on the BIOSYSMO applications that emerge through the development of individual KERs. In this scope, the project outcomes, the analysis of external environments that can affect the effective exploitation of BIOSYSMO applications (SWOT, Market landscape), and the potential routes and IPRs are presented on the basis of the aggregated KERs that result in the 5 key BIOSYSMO applications.

3.1 Exploitation Objectives & Strategy

3.1.1 Objectives

Overall, the exploitation activities have been organised in order to deliver a set of objectives including the engagement of stakeholders and exploitation roadmaps, the management of emerging IPRs, innovation management, and delivery of detailed exploitation plans, especially for partners with commercial activities. The exploitation plan will be gradually constructed and updated in parallel with the progress of the project and thus will be further detailed in the mid-term and final version of the “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results, including Communication Activities” (PEDRC).

Figure 15 Objectives of BIOSYSMO exploitation plan

3.1.2 Strategy

The exploitation strategy is based on:

- The definition of Key Exploitation Results and ownership schemes of involved partners.
- The implementation of customizable and effective dissemination activities.
- The preparation of customised business plans adapted to the needs of each partner.

The initial plan of exploitation activities was prepared at proposal stage and presented in the Grant Agreement including the Key Exploitable Results and preliminary routes, IPRs strategy and related markets for each KER and involved partners. The exploitation plan has considered, as a basis, the initially identified KERs for each partner, which in the contexts of this (public) deliverable are considered as raw ingredients for the materialisation of the BIOSYSMO applications. A detailed presentation and analysis of the KERs will be presented in the next (sensitive-confidential) PEDRC versions.

For the purposes of this plan, customised questionnaires have been prepared to collect information on the contribution of beneficiaries to the development of each BIOSYSMO application. The BIOSYSMO key exploitable results reflect the development of five end-user applications. Furthermore, the individual business plans are focused on the BIOSYSMO beneficiaries with strong commercial and research activities; specifically, for IDENER, TAUW, CIIMAR, LEITAT and INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN.

3.1.3 Exploitation activities

The exploitation activities of BIOSYSMO are appropriately distributed with respect to the confidentiality and progress achieved during the project. This 1st PEDRC (public) focusses on the applications and SWOT analyses of the project, the analysis of the main markets associated with BIOSYSMO research activities, and the options for exploitation routes and IPRs adjusted to the specific needs of BIOSYSMO.

In parallel and already in the early stages of project (M6), the KERs list will be updated and validated. For this purpose, customised questionnaires will be prepared, along with questionnaires to monitor preexisting IP that is used in contexts of BIOSYSMO implementation and exploitation contexts. The co-ownership schemes, the specific exploitation routes and IPRs per KER will be cleared. This (confidential) information will be presented in the second PEDRC together with the initial individual business plans of partners (CANVAS and external environments) with intense commercial activities. In the 3rd PEDRC, the IPRs strategy, the Results Ownership List, and the individual business plans will be updated as summarised in the following table.

Table 8 Distribution of exploitation activities during the project

	1 st PEDRC M6 (Public)	2 nd PEDRC M24 (Sensitive-Confidential)	3 rd PEDRC M48 (Sensitive-Confidential)
KERs description & analysis		✓	
Applications analysis	✓		
Background knowledge		✓	
SWOT	✓	✓ (update)	
PESTLE		✓	
MARKET	✓		
IPRs	✓	✓ (update)	✓
Results Ownership List			✓
Individual Business Plans	✓	✓ (update)	✓ (update)
CANVAS		✓	
External environments		✓	✓ (update)
Competition analysis			✓
Internal environments			✓
Financial analysis			✓
Patent analysis		✓	✓
Future exploitation plans			✓

3.2 Project applications

The BIOSYSMO KERs correspond to specific technological solutions that are essentially reflected to the development of five end-user applications in a combined way, as shown in the following Table:

Table 9 BIOSYSMO Applications

Application	Involved partners	Markets
1. Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria-assisted water phytoremediation	IDE, UBU, JSI, LEITAT, TAUW, CNRS	Bioremediation; Biotechnology; Agriculture; Wastewater treatment; Environmental monitoring
2. Combined poplar-microbe biosystems for soil phytoremediation	IDE, JSI, TAUW, UBFC, UPM	
3. Estuarine sediment phytoremediation	IDE, JSI, LEITAT, CIIMAR, CNRS	
4. Treatment of (ground)water with BES reactors	IDE, JSI, LEITAT, CNRS, TAUW	
5. Soil biostimulation and bioaugmentation	IDE, UBU, JSI, TAUW, UBFC, UPM, ICL	

3.2.1 Groups of KERs

To facilitate the definition and analysis steps of exploitation, the KERs list, as initially defined at the proposal stage, has been appropriately grouped over 4 levels:

- ✓ Knowhow (products & processes)
- ✓ Intermediate chemicals and components
- ✓ Products
- ✓ Services

The **Products** category refers to end products (integrated bioremediation systems) available for direct sales in the market. **Intermediate chemicals and components** refer to tangible results and apply to developments utilised as raw/auxiliary materials and components (e.g., screened/engineered strains, consortia structures, and technological equipment) to formulate end products. **Knowhow** on the development of products and processes summarises the KER that includes generated knowledge that is materialised as bioremediation-related methods and strategies and applies to the evaluation of 'How to'. Finally, **services** involve the set of analyses, databases, and models, LCA services, and microbial screening and aggregation services.

3.2.1.1 Application 1: Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria-assisted water phytoremediation

Phytoremediation is implemented with microorganisms that interact with the plant to improve its growth and health and the overall bioremediation of pollutants. Hydroponic systems refer to the growth of plants in water solutions rather than soil. These media will be exposed to contaminated water, simulating conditions for effective bioremediation that will be performed with the use of selected bacteria consortia that are applied to the roots of plants or other carriers. In this way, alternative bioremediation strategies will be monitored and evaluated in terms of achieved conditions such as rhizome, leaves, metal content, pH, turbidity, and roots. Additional strategies will also be addressed by implementing electrodes in hydroponic systems and exploitation of electroactive consortia. Such systems will enable innovation of hybrid Bioelectrochemical Systems (BES) that apply to specific and challenging plant crops.

3.2.1.2 Application 2: Combined poplar-microbe biosystems for soil phytoremediation

Endophytes are microorganisms that (if they can evade the plant's defense) enter, live, and interact strongly with the plant. In BIOSYSMO, bacteria and fungi with high metal and organics accumulation capabilities are targeted. To facilitate colonisation of selected microorganisms with plant tissue (and penetrate its defence), naturally modified poplar lines will be developed as carriers of microorganisms. The needed traits will be explored by investigating natural changes on gene activities and expression either by exposing such lines to specific external/environmental conditions and/or by evolution and natural growth. The symbiotic poplar-microbial biosystems will be tested for Hg, Cd, and organic sequestration, improving health of the rhizosphere. The impact of microbial diversity and the poplar physiologies achieved will be tested to maximise the bioremediation capabilities of the biosystem. Greenhouse facilities will be used to develop such hybrid biosystems.

3.2.1.3 Application 3: Estuarine sediment phytoremediation

To simulate estuarine water and nutrients contained, plants and sediments are watered with saline solutions, while irrigation is used to simulate tidal conditions. The modelled estuarine systems will be investigated under greenhouse conditions, where bacteria aggregations will be inoculated into the water system to examine bioaugmentation and removal of contaminants from the affected sediments and plant tissues. To this end, microplastics will also be considered as potential pollutants for biodegradation.

3.2.1.4 Application 4: Treatment of (ground)water with BES reactors

Bioelectrochemical Systems (BES) utilize electroactive microbes that are capable of processing contaminated (ground)water. BIOSYSMO will develop microstructured biofilms to be implemented on BES electrodes for improved microbial performance. The configuration will test water treatment at both the anode and the cathode, enabling oxidation and reduction chemistries for the removal of various pollutants, such as hydrocarbons, antibiotics, metals, etc. Alternative techniques will be tested for the development of biofilms (dipped or sprayed electrodes with microbes), while a cascade of BES will be implemented to maximise working volumes against energy and costs of additional devices.

3.2.1.5 Application 5: Soil biostimulation and bioaugmentation

Bioaugmentation is applied to remediate contaminated soils with the use of microbes. BIOSYSMO will investigate the use of genetically modified microbial strains with high pollutants sequestration capabilities. A step further, alternative biostimulation strategies will be investigated, which essentially relate to the applied soil conditions that affect bioaugmentation. To this end, alternative chemical environments will be tested and optimised in terms of chemicals, fertilisers, and physicochemical factors, such as nutrients, temperature, pH, salinity, moisture, etc.

3.2.2 Impact

3.2.2.1 Environment

The application of a nature-based solution for the removal of mixed contaminants promotes the protection of water and marine resources, soil revitalization, pollution control (water, soil and air) and the overall protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems. For the general society, this will increase their quality of life from the reduced pollution, green areas revitalisation, and water, air and soil safety. Biotechnology applications will be respectful of the environment, while recovering soil health and water and air quality. Plant use will not only remove contaminants from water and sediments, but will also enhance and improve soil structural properties and stability; provide habitats for important flora and fauna; and contribute to the reduction of carbon dioxide. In this scope, the following will be achieved: reduced environmental footprints; improvements in pollution remediation technologies; protection and recovery of degraded ecosystems and biodiversity.

It is evident that the optimised bioremediation technologies will have a positive impact in terms of sustainability and environmental care, since our focus is to take advantage of nature-based solutions to clean up the environment, by also decreasing the synthetic inputs and energy required. The environmental impact will be estimated using tools such as LCA and the environmental risk assessment of associated technologies.

3.2.2.2 Policy-making

All applications address the reduction of pollution and the recovery of soil and water resources to 'good status' in accordance with the European Green Deal, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the Soil Strategy, and the 8th Environmental Action Programme. The EU Water Framework Directive is currently under revision, which is another area of impact of the project.

In particular, the development of healthy symbiotic relationships between microbial communities and plants (App 1, App 2, App 3 and, to some extent, App 4 because BES will also be combined with App 1), have the potential to create ecosystems that will support additional biodiversity (insects, fish, birds, etc.). The use of communities of diverse plant species represents an interesting solution aligned with European Green Deal targets, like the provision of ecosystem services, aligned with the EU Pollinators Initiative, the Birds Directive, and the Habitats Directive, thus contributing to the EU Biodiversity Strategy goals, while also restoring damaged and unattractive landscapes that were altered and degraded in the past.

In addition, bioremediation and phytoremediation strategies are useful tools within the biobased circular economy, as interesting circular business cases contributing to the New Circular Economy Action Plan and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy could be developed; for example, metal biorecovery (App 1 and App 4) or biomass exploitation (App 1 and App 2). Furthermore, application 2 includes the study/development of genetically modified poplar lines using new genomic techniques (NGT). The results in this regard may have an impact on the development/update of future GMO regulations related to the application of NGT (e.g., providing data about safety). Likewise, NGT techniques will be applied to microorganisms (mainly orientated to App 5), whose results may have similar implications. Additionally, white papers will be prepared in the area of sustainability. These could be used for lobbying thinktanks and charities with an interest in the area, research funding bodies, and scientific committees.

Policymakers will benefit from a scientifically proven solution to help solve the growing problem of soil and water pollution. The evaluation of the solutions (environmental, economic, safety and social impacts) is going to help to set recommendations for new regulations within a beneficial regulatory framework for bioremediation strategies. This will also contribute to the reduction of costs resulting from pollution management and its negative effects on public health and services of the services of the estuarine ecosystem.ecosystem.

3.3 BIOSYSMO PARTNERS

3.3.1 Commercial partners

3.3.1.1 IDENER

IDENER RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT AGRUPACION DE INTERES ECONOMICO is located in the Aerópolis Science and Technology Park (Seville, Spain) and its main research

activities involve Modeling & Simulation, Mathematical programming, Optimization and Software development. The company has extensive research experience, having participated in 13 H2020, 1 ISF and 16 Horizon Europe projects, holding the role of coordinator in 4 of them; 64% of IDENER's employees are Ph.D. researchers; its income is based on international research; its turnover increases by 48%. In contexts of BIOSYSMO, besides project management, IDENER offers its expertise in machine learning, big data analysis, bioinformatics, and synthetic biology in applied biosystems, GEM modelling, genetic engineering, and process modelling. IDENER targets the development of cross-referenced databases of biodegradation resources, model-based development of metabolic pathways, and strains with improved performance in biodegradation of pollutants.

3.3.1.2 TAUW GmbH

TAUW is a European firm in the field of environmental and sustainability consulting. TAUW has in its operations more than 1200 employees and has facilities in six countries

across Europe (Netherlands, Germany, Belgium, Italy, France, Spain). Regarding BIOSYSMO activities, the company is involved in consulting and management of water, soil, and groundwater treatment and environmental monitoring. The company will provide engineering consulting and novel remediation strategies for soil and water treatment, as well as will offer access to sites for sampling and field testing of BIOSYSMO technologies, providing real-life perspectives to research activities.

Figure 16 Overall profile of TAUW GmbH

3.3.1.3 Blue Synergy

Blue Synergy is an SME that provides social, environmental, sustainability and eco-design services. In the context of BIOSYSMO, Blue Synergy will perform a sustainability analysis of the developed bioremediation systems to demonstrate the advantages and benefits of BIOSYSMO technologies compared to standard physicochemical treatment methods. The analysis will include a) life cycle assessment, b) life cycle costing analysis and c) social impacts analysis. The company will gain a wide experience in the sustainability analysis of high-tech bioremediation systems. This knowledge will be classified and stored in Blue Synergy's internal Knowledge databases. This know-how will be used and included in Blue Synergy's services focused on the analysis of remediation systems. Participation in the BIOSYSMO project will increase the prestige of the company, allowing it to increase the portfolio of its customers in the chemical and remediation industries.

3.3.2 R&D partners

3.3.2.1 CIIMAR

CIIMAR is an Interdisciplinary Centre for Marine and Environmental Research that operates under the University of Porto. The research centre promotes understanding of Biological, Physical and Chemical dynamics Ocean and coastal areas and provides

innovative solutions and products (e.g., marine products) to deal with economic, environmental, and societal challenges in our days. Its activities also include ecosystem health monitoring, aquaculture optimisation, and biotechnology for the development of human and environmental health. Customised solutions address industrial needs, water quality, and mitigation of risks from contamination targeting to the preservation of ecosystems.

CIIMAR is involved in the development of novel plant-microbe systems, whose use can be directly extrapolated to the development of Nature-based bioremediation solutions that can be transferred from the laboratory to the field (estuarine areas). To this end, CIIMAR holds a valuable library of isolated microbial collections from estuarine environments with biodegradation capabilities. Thus, CIIMAR will perform: i) sample collection from the polluted estuaries of Douro and Lima and its characterisation in

terms of contamination and microbial diversity; ii) isolation of microorganisms with degrading capabilities; iii) development of novel microbial consortiums with bioremediation potential; iv) optimisation of the efficiency of the developed consortiums in microcosm experiments; v) conducting mesocosm experiments mimicking estuarine conditions and; vi) applying on-site the best biosystem solution.

The Research centre will benefit from knowledge on the contamination and microbiome at polluted sites, as well as knowledge on cultures with degrading microorganisms. CIIMAR will also benefit from developing an integrated approach for designing enhanced microbial-assisted phytoremediation biosystems bringing new opportunities for collaborations with companies and for commercial exploitation (spin-offs, industrial use, technology developments, new processes and advisory services).

3.3.2.2 INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN

The Jožef Stefan Institute is located in Slovenia and focuses on applied and basic research. It holds more than 1000 employees in the fields of engineering, life and natural sciences. The institute is structured over four main

Jožef Stefan Institute

research departments for (i) Physics, (ii) Chemistry & Biochemistry, (iii) Electronics and Information Technologies, and (iv) Reactor Engineering and Energetics, which further involve 29 divisions focussing on Theoretical Physics, Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Environmental Sciences, Systems and Control, Communication Systems, Computer Systems, Intelligent Systems, Reactor Engineering, etc.

In the context of BIOSYSMO, the Jožef Stefan Institute specializes in the field of colloid chemistry & biology and will contribute to the development of bioremediation systems in microfluidic scales.

3.3.2.3 LEITAT association

Leitat has its origin in the non-profit association of Acondicionamiento Tarrasense, which was founded in 1906 in Spain by a team of industrialists. The mission of Leitat is to provide research and technology research and to offer sustainable

economic, industrial, environmental, and social value to its clients (companies and other entities). Leitat also has strong collaborations with key industrial actors and bodies, like BASF, Renishaw, HP and ACCIÓ.

Some of its research directions related to the BIOSYSMO research and innovation activities include contaminated water treatment (municipal, process, industrial), Bioelectrochemical Systems, Nature-based solutions and disinfection and conditioning technologies. Leitat is strongly focused on improving human and environmental safety especially in terms of pollutants identification (i.e. of microplastics, metals, chemicals) and exposure assessment. To this end, the partner will contribute to the development and optimisation of bioremediation systems supported by BES configurations for the treatment of water pollutants.

3.3.2.4 Universidad de Burgos

The University of Burgos was established in 1994 (Spain) and has 10.000 students involved in undergraduate, master and Ph.D. studies. In the context of BIOSYSMO, UBU will optimise a phytoremediation technology on a laboratory scale, initially as an individual technology and next as part of a hybrid technology. UBU will take advantage of previous results concerning phytoremediation applied to groundwater contaminated by heavy metals, as well as will deep explore assisted PGPR phytoremediation and study the behaviour of the plant species selected in terms of key molecular responses. UBU will also continue to optimise biostimulation and bioaugmentation strategies to bioremediate complex pollutants, such as hydrocarbons and pesticides. Genetically modified bacterial strains with a high potential for contaminants degradation will be applied in both laboratory experiments and real soil samples.

Having as a starting point the outcomes from the previous EU funded research project, GREENER, the improvement of TRL of the above-mentioned technology will be a clear benefit by strengthening its bioremediation research lines and strengthening collaborations, and agreements with associated end-users and enterprises promoting knowledge transfer.

3.3.2.5 CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS

CNRS is a leading research institution in France involved in a wide spectrum of research areas, such as biological sciences, chemistry, ecology, physics, information sciences, engineering, etc. Consequently, the CNRS is structured in 10 institutes that collaborate with each other. In BIOSYSMO, CNRS will focus on the development of efficient analytical protocols (e.g., μ LC-MS/MS). Innovative green analytical solutions will be investigated for reliable and efficient analysis of complex pollutants taking advantage of STA instrumentation.

3.3.2.6 Universite Bourgogne - Franche – Comte (UBFC)

UBFC comprises a group of universities and institutions and has initiated its activities since 2015. UBFC has highlighted three key pillars of research: (i) Advanced materials, waves, intelligent systems, (ii) Territories, environment, food and (iii) Integrated personalised care. In this context, the UBFC and UFC partners will take advantage of the expertise in symbiotic biosystems between microbes and plants and will contribute to the development of poplar endophytes for phytoremediation applications.

3.3.2.7 Universidad Politecnica de Madrid (UPM)

UPM was founded in 1971 and is structured over several centres and campus that host the different scientific and research faculties and facilities. The university owns greenhouse facilities that would be used in contexts of BIOSYSMO for plant growth, testing and screening plant phenotyping. UPM will contribute to the development of modified microbe-plant symbiotic biosystems. Based on extensive experience in genetics, UPM will address the mechanisms of poplar models and their responses to the various environmental conditions that are exposed.

3.3.2.8 Imperial College London

The University of Imperial College London participates in the SynBio and Evolution lab. Imperial has participated in several research projects in the past years related to the fields of fields of biotechnology and bioprocessing. ICL will investigate bacterial strains capable of degrading pollutants and the biochemical pathways involved in these processes. In this scope, the research group will also engineer model microorganisms to optimise the removal of pollutants and investigate strategies to boost natural metabolic processes through the controlled supply of nutrients and other probiotics. Net-zero and circular economy approaches are a strategic research priority for ICL. There is a less likely but still significant path to IP protection (patents) and commercialisation.

3.4 External environments

A preliminary analysis of the external environments has been performed to identify key issues that are capable of positively and negatively affecting the sustainable exploitation of the BIOSYSMO generated results and developed applications.

3.4.1 Project SWOT Analysis

Strengths		Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature-based solutions • Monitoring and transition of processes from laboratory scales to real-life conditions • Multidisciplinary approach • Partners bringing knowledge from real-life environments (fields testing) • Selection of more sustainable solutions • New guidelines to control the environmental release of pollutants 	Internal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of policy measures to implement bioremediation strategies • Biotechnology costs • Public awareness • Lack of investments in bioremediation R&D
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safer and widely accepted bioremediation technologies • Tracked and updated exploitation and IP issues to suitably benefit partners for each case 	External	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidentiality, access and/or licensing issues for available data • Lack of LCA data due to innovative research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Mitigation: use external sources (stakeholders), publicly available (literature) or licensed (if needed, under logic terms) data</i>
Opportunities		Threats

3.4.2 Market Analysis

This section focusses on the major markets related to the research and innovation fields of BIOSYSMO. The analysis highlights the sizes, the market segments, and trends that favour or limit growth of associated markets. Inherently, five key global markets are identified regarding (i) bioremediation, (ii)

biotechnology, (iii) agriculture, (iv) wastewater treatment, and (v) environmental monitoring. Bioremediation guides the research activities of BIOSYSMO at its core. Biotechnology constitutes a key element for the investigation of key solutions, while agriculture, wastewater treatment and environmental monitoring comprise of key markets to absorb the BIOSYSMO solutions and applications.

3.4.2.1 Bioremediation

The size of the global bioremediation market in 2021 has been valued at \$ 12B and is expected to hold a strong CAGR of 10% towards 2030. The bioremediation market is segmented by type of service (Figure 17) over 3 main categories, where soil (38%) and wastewater (31%) hold the lion’s share of the global market – also the main applications of BIOSYSMO activities – while contaminated oilfields follow in order.

Figure 17: Bioremediation market segments by type of service¹⁴

Industrial developments have inherited a wide environmental contamination (e.g., in fresh water, soil, agriculture, etc), which in turn drives the needs for intensified bioremediation and innovation. The disposal of plastics, chemicals, and oil spills as well as GHG emissions, all advocate to even worse environmental impacts that make indispensable the existence of bioremediation services.¹⁴ The market segment that utilizes microbes has a value of \$ 47M (2021) and has an expected growth of 11% (driving to 2030).¹⁵

¹⁴ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/bioremediation-market-report>

¹⁵ <https://www.biospace.com/article/microbial-bioremediation-market-size-worth-usd-94-992-7-million-in-2030-emergen-research/>

Furthermore, the increase in the use of protective equipment and face masks (due to the COVID19 pandemic) has increased the disposal of medical waste that further increases the need for bioremediation. Furthermore, bioremediation is required to limit contamination by infectious microorganisms and viruses, such as SARS-CoV-2. In the EU, more than 2.8 million contaminated sites have been counted associated with health consequences and high mortality rates. Other solutions – competitive with bioremediation strategies – include the use of chemical (oxidising agents, absorbents) and electrochemical treatment; however, most options appear to have low efficiency, higher costs, and limited adaptation to different cases.¹⁴

3.4.2.2 Biotechnology

The global market of biotechnology has been valued at \$ 1T (2021) and the growth of the market is expected to reach up to 14%, paving the way to 2030. The continuous developments in the field of Machine Learning in combination with advancements in computer sciences and technologies enabled scaling and growth of the biotechnology sector. In the presence of recent health challenges (COVID19 pandemic) and the strong fight against chronic diseases (cancer) and infections, the biotechnology market has grown with strong steady growth. For example, the COVID19 pandemic mobilised the development of 11 billion vaccine doses, which covered almost half of the world's population. The market is also driven by the modernized regulatory landscape so much at EU and global level.¹⁶

Biotechnology is associated with a wide spectrum of applications in the field of genetically modified organisms (e.g., crops, insect-resistant seeds) and microorganisms, e.g., to impart specific traits and/or overproduce biomass and/or specific chemicals. The latter is related to the research activities and developments of BIOSYSMO. Specifically, the segments of the biotechnology market

- Health
- Food & Agriculture
- Natural Resources & Environment
- Industrial Processing
- Bioinformatics
- Other applications

Figure 18 Biotechnology market segments by application

by application (Figure 18) are mainly covered by health applications (50%), while food and agriculture, natural resources & environment and industrial processing follow in order. In this context, the

¹⁶ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/biotechnology-market>

agriculture and environment segments comprise almost 30% of the market and constitute the two main segments of BIOSYSMO activities.

As shown in Figure 19,¹⁷ North America holds the largest share of the biotechnology market by 40% (2021), while Europe follows together with Asia Pacific by almost 20% each; East, Africa and Latin America own the lowest shares of 10% each. The budget spent for biotechnology R&D in India raised to \$ 228M.¹⁸

Figure 19 Biotechnology market shares by region

Consequently, the key players worldwide involved in the biotechnology market are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20 Key players in the global biotechnology market

¹⁷ <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/biotechnology-market>

¹⁸ <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/4396357/global-biotechnology-market-size-share-and>

To identify trends in biotechnology and the potential market penetration of BIOSYSMO achievements in biotechnology, it is necessary to delve into the specific components and launched applications over the covered segments and subsectors of the global market. The breakdown of the biotechnology components includes applications applied for bacteria, enzymes production, fungus, animal, plants, etc; all reflect to the biotechnology research and innovation areas of interest. Specifically, plant biotechnology holds the lion’s share of 35%, while bacteria follow with a score of 14%. Genome editing (also included in BIOSYSMO activities) is fourth in row, referring to the 9% of biotechnology components. All 3 metrics highlight trends that are particularly considered in BIOSYSMO justifying that the project is involved in biotechnology fields of high interest that hold high market shares (and potential clientele).

Figure 21 Breakdown of biotechnology components

A step further, the biotechnology categories and presence in associated markets and segments are monitored. The number of plant biotechnology categories comes third in row, after medical, chemicals, and food, while the great majority of them are either under development or at early-stage concept, justifying multiple pipelines to drive BIOSYSMO results to the market. Soil amendment and threat detection hold lower market shares and are mainly under development and at early stages.¹⁹

¹⁹ <https://www.futurebioengineeredproducts.org/product-analysis/>

Figure 22 Maturity of biotechnology market categories

3.4.2.3 Agriculture

Activities in agriculture have an apparent impact on soil and water contamination, which essentially calls for bioremediation services. In this context, it is indispensable to be aware of the conditions and trends of the global agriculture market to reveal critical insights about the penetration of BIOSYSMO results into the bioremediation and agriculture-related markets.

The size of the global agriculture market raises to more than \$ 11T (2021) and is expected to have a CAGR of 8.2% by 2026. Considering that the world population is expected to reach 10 billion by 2050, it is naturally expected that it accordingly affects agriculture growth due to increased food demand. For example, an increase in cereal production is expected to be 13% (2027). The COVID-19 pandemic inferred a huge decrease of the agriculture market due to disrupted supply chains and limitation in trade and consumption (lockdowns).²⁰

In parallel, there is a huge effort from agriculture actors and associated investors toward its transformation into smart agriculture, whose market share rises to \$ 14 billion and is expected to have a high CAGR of 11% (2030). Smart agriculture aims to take advantage of all new technological achievements and features including both software and hardware infrastructure. Its application includes biometrics and monitoring, use of sensors, robotics, drones, and advanced data processing, such as the use of machine learning and AI. Smart agriculture also considers real-time data on soil, water, air, and crops conditions to maximise production and sustainability and minimise use of auxiliaries (fertilisers, chemicals, water, etc.) and environmental impacts.

²⁰ <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/agriculture-global-market-report>

In this scope, BIOSYSMO applications and technology control can be ideally integrated with smart agriculture practises to biologically remediate surrounding environments of agriculture activities, thus minimising dispersal and contamination of soil, water, and air of neighbouring areas.²¹ In the same sense, the implementation of smart greenhouses, which integrate monitoring and water, fertilisers, and energy management, can directly incorporate in situ bioremediation solutions. To this end, smart agriculture is mainly covered by activities (Figure 23) related to yield monitoring applications (44%), while field mapping (16%), labour management (10%) and crop scouting (10%) follow in order.

Figure 23 Agriculture market segments by precision farming application

From a geographical point of view, smart agriculture is blooming in North America, holding a market share of 45% (2021) and expecting a CAGR of 9.5% towards 2030, which is also strongly supported at the governmental level. At the same time, Asia-Pacific also expects high growth at the same period. The growth in both regions reveal a strong clientele pool for the BIOSYSMO research outcomes and applications.²²

3.4.2.4 Treatment of wastewater

Water and wastewater treatment constitute key applications markets of the exploitable results of BIOSYSMO. The market has been valued at \$ 282B and is expected to follow a CAGR of 7% towards 2027. With only 1% of the the available water on the earth being freshwater, the world faces key challenges in the the protection and remediation of water basins and the the minimising of pollution. The technological advancements and the continuously stricter legislative environment are going to favour the market increase, while, on the other side, the cost, competition, and restrained investments are going to limit the increase of the market. The market has been negatively impacted in the COVID-19 pandemic due to postponed activities and investments by involved actors due to disrupted supply

²¹ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/smart-agriculture-farming-market>

²² <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/smart-agriculture-market>

chains and quarantine. A typical paradigm is that of North America, where the market has fallen by 7.3% from 2019 to 2020.²³

Figure 24 Market size of water and wastewater treatment in North America (2018-2022)

The activities of the general market are segmented by 10% into used chemicals, 25% into equipment, while the majority (65%) is held by related services. By source, the market is related to water and wastewater from municipal activities by a huge share of 72%, while the rest (28%) refers to industrial wastewater treatment.

Based on the segmentation of technology for process water treatment, several technologies have been identified to extrapolate for other paradigms of water / wastewater treatment (Figure 25). Thermal, chemical and mechanical technologies (e.g. distillation, chlorination and filters) hold the lions share, while other technologies, where biological is included, own 44% of the market's technologies.²⁴

²³ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/amp/water-and-wastewater-treatment-market-102632>

²⁴ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/process-water-treatment-market-A15544>

Figure 25 Process wastewater market segments by applied technology

Overall, five key players of the market from Europe (e.g. SUEZ Worldwide, Kemira, ASIO), 8 from the US (e.g. DuPont, 3M, Xylem, Evoqua Water Technologies, American Water, Aquatech International, BioMicrobics) and 4 from other countries/continents (e.g. Hydro International, Trojan Technologies, Kurita Water Industries Ltd).

3.4.2.5 Environmental monitoring

One of the key outcomes of BIOSYSMO is the development of analytical methods for the assessment of the environment to manage pollution risks. The expected results are associated with the activities met in the environmental monitoring market, whose size is estimated at almost \$ 20B (2020) and is expected to follow a CAGR of 8.2% paving the way to 2030. The applications target monitoring key environmental factors like humidity, airflow, temperature, and pollutants. In this scope, the market is fragmented by monitoring components as shown in Figure 26 (left). The particulates own the largest share (35%), while biological and chemical detection sum 44% of the market monitoring activities; conditions, like temperature sensing and moisture detection, follow in order to reach 20% of monitoring components. Segmentation of environmental monitoring by application (Figure 26, right) comprises of air, water, soil, and noise environmental factors. BIOSYSMO is directly involved in water and soil conditions monitoring, which reach almost half (47%) of the market economic activities.²⁵

²⁵ [https:// www.alliedmarketresearch.com/environmental-monitoring-market](https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/environmental-monitoring-market)

Segment by Component

Segment by Application

Figure 26 Market segments by components (Left) and by Application (right)

Other segmentations involve Environmental Monitors, Environmental Sensors and Wearable Monitors, while key players in the field, with which potential collaborations can be viewed, include Emerson Electric Co., General Electric, Siemens AG, Honeywell International Inc., 3M, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., etc.

The main drivers and incentives for environment monitoring are natural and obvious. The need to sustainably manage and exploit natural resources (air, water, land, fisheries, etc) is indispensable for humanity. Moreover, environmental monitoring facilitates and accelerates the prevention of environmental incidents (regional, global) that can affect so much nutrition and neighbouring societies and ecosystems. Key limitations are traditional methods and instrumentation that require time and money, as well as accuracy of the latter. The technological advancements over the last years have addressed and offer improvements in both constraints. Regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, despite the need for continuous monitoring of virus infections at several areas (e.g., rivers, municipal wastes, etc.), the disruption of supply chains and the limited manufacturing and human activities resulted in a limited demand for monitoring of pollutants (2020).²⁶

The legislative landscape includes, already since 1992, policies and strategies for abatement of environmental pollution.^{27, 28} Similarly, the National Water policy (2002) provides guidelines for

²⁶ <https://www.meticulousresearch.com/product/environmental-monitoring-market-5024>

²⁷ Policy statement for abatement of pollution, 1992

²⁸ National Conservation Strategy and the Policy Statement on Environmental & Development, 1992

conservation and appropriate management of water resources, while recently EU has taken initiatives and laws (EU Climate Law) through the EU Green Deal and its specific goals for climate actions towards zero pollution and protection of EU/global earth elements achieving cleaner air and water, healthy soil and biodiversity.^{29,30}

3.5 Exploitation routes

Before focussing on the specific exploitation routes for each result, it is indispensable to clarify and understand the different types and nature of results. This will reveal new aspects on how to commercialize each product, application and knowledge. For this purpose, the main categories of exploitable results are mentioned below to appropriately classify BIOSYSMO applications into each category. The categories and the definition of type of result are as follows:

- **Processes:** ways to make other products (tangible or not) or do/accomplish other activities
- **Equipment:** to make products using processes
- **Knowledge & IP:** reflects valuation of “how to”
- **Standards:** the process of implementing and developing technical standards
- **Software:** code (maybe algorithm, too)
- **Other:** Platform, publications, databases, patent, etc.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Provision of guidelines (e.g. through reports and workshops) and presenting analysis results and/or conclusions
- **Services:** by offering the above products, processes, equipment, or knowledge.

Typical examples of the BIOSYSMO results that are fully aligned with the above categories include:

- ✓ bioremediation databases
- ✓ processes/strategies
- ✓ mathematical models and algorithms for data analysis

²⁹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

³⁰ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/environmental-monitoring-market-216846315.html>

- ✓ methods and know-how for systems development
- ✓ equipment components
- ✓ improved strains
- ✓ integrated systems

All the above are appropriately distributed to explore and address the needs of specific partners and end users that can be identified both inside and outside the project. As shown in Table 10, the following types of partner/user are identified in contexts of BIOSYSMO activities, and these are researchers, industrial users/investors, policymakers, the general public, and civil society. Each category is interested in different types of results as distributed in each column of Table 10. This structure can further assist in the definition of appropriate exploitation routes (and dissemination activities) that optimally match BIOSYSMO results with potential stakeholders. The table can also assist in searching and filtering candidate stakeholders to approach.

Table 10 Exploitable Results per Type of Partner

Research Communities	Industry / innovators	Policymakers	Civic Society
Data	Software	Policy Recommendations	Skills, Knowledge
Softwares	Prototypes		
Methodology	Know How		
Algorithm	Process		
Scientific publication	Database		
Process			

Data, software, and methods/algorithms are expected to be developed especially addressing the interests of the research community, while applications, Bioelectrochemical Systems, bioremediation processes and strategies are aligned with commercial interests of industrial stakeholders and investors. Policymakers can take advantage of the best recommendations for effective soil and water remediation remediation to achieve the the necessary goals for clean and healthy ecosystems that benefit EU / global citizens. Finally, there are specific technology and workforce skills that can be exploited by

existing and incoming professionals, students,, and the the general public, who can also also be aware of the new advanced means of recovering polluted sites. Having identified, understood, and distributed the different types of results to different interested parties, the potential exploitation routes for each BIOSYSMO result and application will be appropriately considered.

Potential BIOSYSMO exploitation routes can be defined as market-orientated, scientific, and other types. Universities and research-related organisations are naturally and mostly (or exclusively) orientated to scientific-based exploitation routes. The **scientific exploitation routes** can be further defined as:

- ✓ Publications (scientific articles and magazines)
- ✓ Participation in conferences
- ✓ Subsequent research activities based on project results
- ✓ Embedding new knowledge and expertise in teaching activities
- ✓ Opening of new opportunities for researchers (PhD thesis and post-docs)
- ✓ Further participation in research, which can be materialised through future research, innovation, and development projects (EU, national, individual).

Companies inherently follow market-orientated exploitation routes, without excluding cases (especially some SMEs) that are also interested in the above scientific routes by holding an intense research profile. Market-orientated **exploitation routes** are defined as

- ✓ Direct Sales of product/Service
- ✓ Sell IP rights
- ✓ License IP rights
- ✓ Transfer ownership of IP rights to another partner from the consortium
- ✓ Cooperation agreement/Joint venture
- ✓ Implementation in your own company/internal exploitation
- ✓ Provision of services/consultancy

As mentioned above, other types of exploitation routes are identified, especially when other types of end-user groups (e.g. policymakers and the general public) in planning exploitation activities. Such **other types of exploitation routes** could include:

- ✓ Policy brief or roadmap

- ✓ Societal activity
- ✓ Policy change
- ✓ Standardization activities

3.6 IPRs strategy

An initial IPRs strategy has been presented at the proposal stage, where all beneficiaries have already agreed to protect both preexisting (background) knowledge and the foreground generated during the project. Specifically, the generated results are owned by the partner that created them and will be responsible to decide the means of protecting them. When the results are generated by several partners, then all partners will own such results and decide on the protection of the results. The preexisting knowledge has been defined in the Consortium agreement, where the means of using it for implementation and exploitation purposes have been defined. Moreover, that background will be royalty-free to the consortium during the project for the execution of project research and innovation activities. Access to both background and foreground after the project will be licenced or granted under reasonable and fair conditions as defined by the (co)owner(s) of the results/application.

To ensure effective exploitation of KERs the consortium has already defined at proposal stage, and in accordance with the identified BIOSYSMO applications (Section 3.2.1.), the specific/desired IPR means to protect the results. This plan will be continuously updated and detailed during the project, in line with the expected maturity of results, through the following confidential versions of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), including communication activities; namely, D7.4 on M24 and D7.5 on M48. In this scope, the BIOSYSMO consortium will consider (during the project) the whole spectrum of Intellectual Property protection tools to ensure best practises for protection and post-project exploitation. That is the challenge to conceptually and timely align the IPRs with innovation identified during the project, and with the expected results and the continuously updated exploitation routes. In parallel, additional challenges appear with respect to the definition and agreement (among partners) of partner ownership rates for the applications to which they contribute.

To cope with the the above challenges and build the best feasible exploitation and IPRs management plan, BIOSYSMO has a 5-level toolbox to customise and implement before, during,, and after the project as follows:

- 1) The consortium has already effectively identified and defined the preliminary expected research results and their exploitation routes as a preliminary list of expected/desired IPRs for each result/application in which each partner is involved (proposal stage).
- 2) The consortium has defined the background knowledge and preexisting Intellectual Property to regulate the conditions of collaboration among beneficiaries, as well as has defined the initial exploitation and IPRs management plan through the Grant Agreement configuring the cooperation between the consortium and the EC (at the beginning of the project).
- 3) The Exploitation and Innovation manager (AXIA) of the project will prepare and share customised questionnaires to monitor progress, innovation, and optimise data collection and its processing concerning the generated results, the desired/feasible exploitation routes, and IPR tools (during the project).
- 4) Questionnaires, interviews, and mitigation approaches are considered to identify ownership rates of partners, to guide and assist in the finalisation of ownership rate of each partner for each project result (during the project).
- 5) This and the following versions of the PEDR will summarise, detail, and update all aspects of the exploitation routes and embedded IPR tools to prepare the conditions for effective post-project exploitation (guidance reports for use during and after the project).

Overall, this public PEDR and its following (confidential) versions will further update and detail on the specific Key Exploitable Results of the project, its exploitation routes, the external / internal environment, external / internal environment, the selected IPR tools, and ownership rates for each partner and for each KER, as well as will consult all partners for effective protection of their results and exploitation plans through individual business plans. Being at the beginning of the project, the consortium will still consider all potential IPR means to make the best decisions. To this end, the following available IPR means are considered:

- **Patent:** It is granted by an authority and enables the owner to prevent other entities from commercialising the idea. The result can be commercialised by the owner by granting licences for use, for example, the use of an integrated system for bioremediation; otherwise, it can be free, like an open-source environment. It applies for new knowledge and developments that are not public until the date of application. Exclusivity is ensured for a limited time, which is maximum for 20 years, and exists with a specified geographical region, e.g., country, Europe, worldwide.

- **Utility model:** it protects inventions with lower levels of inventiveness and is valid for 6-10 years. The owner can prevent others from making, offering, using, or selling the products without the owner's permission. Due to its structure, utility models are useful in cases of incrementing inventions.
- **Trademarks:** refers to distinctive signs that are related to specific goods and services. They usually involve the cases of signs, words, logos, colours, sounds, or any combination of these. Trademarks are registered with trademark offices and last for 10 years.
- **Industrial design:** It is a means to protect the appearance of a product that is resulted from its lines, colours, shape and materials. It restricts third parties from selling, offering, importing/exporting or using products with such designs. The function of the product is not protected by this IPR, but by a patent. This IPR applies for a maximum of 25 years.
- **Copyright:** this IPR provides exclusive rights to control the use and economic exploitation, such as translation, reproduction, and distribution of the work. This IPR tool is best for literary work, software and databases, drawings, and others, while it is applied only for the expression of ideas and not the ideas themselves; the ideas can be better protected by means of utility models and patents. This IPR does not require a registration at the EU level, since it is granted at the time of creation.
- **Trade secrets: They consist** of confidential information that is not disclosed to a wide range of people, and they have great commercial value, even though they are not patentable. Key examples are algorithms, R&D information, recipes, and formulas, as well as they can take other forms like a business method, pricing information, process know-how etc; all can be considered as secrets. Since it is a secret, no one should see or have access to this knowledge; therefore, no registration is required. Some tools that are normally used to secure such secret information could be a non-disclosure agreement, non-compete clauses or memorandum of understanding.

In this version of PEDR, Trade Secrets, Copyright, Utility Models, and Patents are considered for the protection of the BIOSYSMO key exploitable results.

Moreover, and keeping in mind the types and groups of identified project results and applications, the following table can be consulted to appropriately make decision for the protection of each result.

Table 11 Typical means of protection for different types of results

Type of results	Patent	Utility	Industrial Design	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information	Trade Secret
Invention	X	X				X	X
Software	X			X		X	X
Scientific article				X			
Design of a product			X	X	X		
Name of a product/ service/project					X		
Know-How							
Website			X	X	X		
Business Plans			X	X	X		X
Website			X	X	X		
Data							X
Recipes & Formulas							X
Failed test results							X
Algorithms							X

4 Conclusions

In the first 6-month period of BIOSYSMO, a set of exploitation, dissemination, and communication activities have been carried out.

The dissemination activities included the setup of the project identity, including the communication tools of the project (official templates, brochure, flyer, poster, roll up). Social media accounts were set up and announced. The official BIOSYSMO webpage was launched including detailed information about the project concept, objectives, impacts, the consortium, the cluster and the dissemination and communication toolkit, among others. The plan for further communication and dissemination activities was updated and thoroughly analysed in this deliverable, including upcoming press releases and newsletters, events and workshops, training activities, publications, and outreach and clustering activities. The targets are summarised in Section 2.3, where the achieved milestones will also be monitored.

The planned exploitation activities included the definition of BIOSYSMO applications (in light of confidential Key Exploitable Results), the SWOT and market landscape, the potential impacts, the partners profiles and the expected exploitation routes and IPR means. A key conclusion that emerges from the above analysis is that the continuously growing associated markets, in combination with the identified strengths and opportunities of BIOSYSMO activities, reveal a rather promising external environment for the effective penetration of the project results and partners into the desired markets. Indeed, BIOSYSMO applications apply to market segments with relatively high shares and growth rates, further invigorating the exploitation potential of BIOSYSMO results, when reaching higher TRLs. The identified impacts verify the expectations at the proposal stage and further highlight promising feedback for policy makers. Finally, the partners' profiles and capacities (knowledge, research potential, clientele, and innovation) highlight the large exploitation potential and portend promising penetration to associated/desired markets and future collaborations.

The presented PEDRC will be appropriately updated and presented in further detail in the following PEDCR versions on M24 (D7.4) and M48 (D7.5).

Regarding the activities in T7.1 and T7.2, the next PEDRC version will focus on updating the dissemination and communication efforts of the consortium, as the results will be available during the implementation of the project. Updates to the communication material will be announced and shared with the consortium. The first two newsletters will be available and shared to relevant audiences through LinkedIn and email. The project video will be announced at M12 presenting the project concept and goals in an informative and simple way. All events already finalised, as well as those planned, will be summarised based on the responses of the consortium to the dedicated questionnaires. Social

media platforms and the project website will be regularly updated with BIOSYSMO news. Statistics from audience participation in the BIOSYSMO website and social media platforms will be included showing the audience reach and demographics of the audience, wherever available. Moreover, clustering activities will also progress and will be reported in the following deliverables.

Concerning the activities in T7.3 and T7.4, the next PEDRC versions will further focus on the description of BIOSYSMO KERs, the background knowledge of contributing beneficiaries and the project SWOT/PESTLE analyses that will highlight limitations and potentials to invigorate exploitation potential of KERs. For this purpose, customised questionnaires will be prepared appropriately and shared with all partners during the following period. The exploitation routes, the proposed IPR means, and the ownership schemes for each KER and each involved partner will be accordingly identified. The individual business models will be detailed in terms of the business model CANVAS, unique selling points, external environments, and considering the competition and the financial potential of associated KERs and end-user applications. An analysis of the patent landscape will also be provided and presented in the following PEDRC versions.

5 Risks

Especially in contexts of WP7 activities, the following 2 risks and mitigation measures have been identified, already at the proposal stage.

Risk description	Mitigation Measure
Patent, trademark, or any IPR infringement during the project	A preliminary patent search was carried out at the proposal stage. Task 7.4 will monitor the patent landscape throughout the project.
IPR conflicts among partners (Level of likelihood to occur)	Partners' IP background organised in the Consortium Agreement; IP strategy defined in Task 7.4; Definition of KER owners in the PEDR.

In the context of WP7, no issues have been raised concerning the identified risks, and therefore no mitigation measure was needed to be triggered and followed.